

A STUDY ON THE CONSEQUENCES OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN INDIAN ECONOMY

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Abstract: This study's primary goal is to comprehend the obstacles to sustainable development facing the Indian economy. The Indian government, led by Prime Minister Narendra Modi, is putting a lot of effort into creating propaganda that will last in the country. Implementing the Sustainable Development Goals in 2015, with a commitment to achieving these targets by 2030, was one of his major initiatives. Again, privatization is an additional effort. The government cannot close the revenue gap and achieve its objectives on its own without the help of institutions and private organizations. Once again, the government has implemented a number of supply policies, such as education and training programs, to lower the rate of literacy and raise public awareness of environmental issues.

The prime minister has always committed to offer the required leadership and cooperation for the NITI AAYOG. The government is periodically taking the required action to combat corruption and black money. The term "inclusive growth" receives adequate attention in the eleventh five-year plan. To achieve sound sustainability, inclusive growth aids in closing social, economic, and environmental gaps. As a result, the UNDP, together with other UN agencies, is actively working to promote and assist nations that are implementing sustainable and inclusive growth policies. Developing components include the private sector and civil society. Since its national development goals are centered around sustainable development goals, India has been actively involved in implementing these goals. Prime Minister Narendra Modi's revolutionary catchphrase, "SABKA SAATH SABKA VIKASH" or "COLLECTIVE EFFORT, INCLUSIVE GROWTH," is regarded as the centre piece of India's national development program. Targets including economic growth, infrastructure development, industrialization, and the fight against poverty are primarily centered with the integration of social and impoverished people's empowerment.

Keywords: India, economy, challenges, sustainable development, etc.

INTRODUCTION

Development that meets present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" is the introduction. The definition of sustainable development that is most commonly used was stated in the 1987 report Our Common Future by the Brundtland Commission. The goal of sustainable development (SD) is to create a future for people and the world that is resilient, Sustainable, and inclusive.

India was a major contributor to the creation of the United Nations Sustainable Development Agenda 2030, and the country's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) closely resemble those of its National

Development Agenda. India's success will determine how far the world gets in reaching the SDGs. The SDGs, which have 17 objectives, 169 targets, and 306 national indicators, could be challenging to comprehend and define, and it could be challenging to define and measure progress. The NITI Aayog has taken the lead by issuing the SDG India Index - Baseline Report 2018, which outlines how the SDGs will be monitored in India, while countries around the world argue over how to implement and track progress toward the Goals. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) India Index Baseline Report, which describes the advancements made by India's states and union territories toward accomplishing the 2030 SDG goals, was released by NITI Aayog. NITI Aayog developed the SDG India Index, which includes 13 of the 17 SDGs (not including Goals 12, 13, 14, and 17). Based on a set of 62 National Indicators that monitor the results of the actions and initiatives of the Indian government, the Index assesses how well each State and Union Territory (UT) is doing. With regard to the social, economic, and environmental conditions of the nation, as well as those of its States and Union Territories, the SDG India Index seeks to provide a complete picture.

A comprehensive index that may be used by governments, businesses, civil society organizations, and the general public is the SDG India Index. It was designed to help leaders and changemakers assess how well Indian states and union territories performed in terms of social, economic, and environmental factors by providing an overall assessment of them. Its objective is to monitor India's and its states' advancement toward the 2030 SDGs.

ESSENTIALS OF SUFFICIENT DEVELOPMENT

Economic expansion, social inclusion, and environmental preservation are the three main components of sustainable development. Ensuring their harmony is crucial. Achieving sustainable livelihood, coexisting peacefully with the environment, sustainable economic growth, and the use of appropriate technology are all necessary for sustainable development.

Environmental sustainability: It guarantees the preservation and responsible use of nature by preventing it from being exploited as a limitless supply of resources. Achieving environmental sustainability is facilitated by a number of factors, including water conservation, investment in renewable energy, innovation in sustainable building and architecture, and support for sustainable mobility.

Social sustainability Social sustainability has the potential to improve healthcare, education, and the global distribution of an acceptable and equitable quality of life by promoting gender equality and the development of individuals, communities, and cultures.

Economic Sustainability that creates wealth for everybody while avoiding environmental damage is the main goal of economic sustainability.

Investment as well as fair allocation of financial resources. removing poverty in all of its manifestations and aspects.

Acknowledging the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, the UN Open Working Group has suggested the following objectives for its Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), with particular goals for some of them:

By 2030, all types of poverty must be eradicated worldwide, and severe poverty—which is currently defined as living on less than \$1.25 per day—must be eliminated for everyone.

By 2020, we want to:

- Put an end to hunger, achieve food security and better nutrition, and promote sustainable agriculture;
- Provide inclusive and equitable quality education and opportunities for lifelong learning for all;
- Ensure that water and sanitation are available and managed sustainably for all;
- Ensure that everyone has access to modern, affordable, sustainable, and reliable energy by 2020.
- Encouraging steady, equitable, and productive growth as well as full and productive employment and decent labor for all.
- Maintaining economic growth per capita based on national conditions, with a focus on least-developed countries, where GDP growth should be at least 7% annually.
- Developing robust infrastructure and advocating for sustainable and equitable industrialization.
- Developing dependable, sustainable, and resilient infrastructure, particularly regional and transnational infrastructure, to promote economic growth and human welfare is one way to foster innovation.
- By 2020, lowering inequality both within and between nations.
- By 2020, achieving inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable cities and human settlements.
- Making sure that patterns of consumption and production are sustainable. Taking immediate action to halt and lessen the effects of climate change by building national resilience and capacity to respond to dangers and natural disasters related to climate change.
- By 2020, the goal is to preserve and responsibly utilize the oceans, seas, and marine resources for sustainable development.
- By 2020, we want to have stopped and reversed land degradation and biodiversity loss, managed forests sustainably, fought desertification, and promoted the sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems.
- Encouraging efficient, responsible, and inclusive institutions at all levels and ensuring that everyone has access to justice.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

This research aims to comprehend the obstacles to sustainable development in the Indian economy.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

All of the data used in this study came from secondary sources, including books, journals, websites, and other sources.

CHALLENGES OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN INDIAN ECONOMY

- Urgent action is needed to address the growing inequality between and within nations.
- Compared to adults, young people are more likely to be unemployed.
- Obstacles in the way of attaining gender parity.
- After a protracted decline, there has been an increase in global hunger. Extreme poverty decreased from 36% in 1990 to 8.6% in 2018, but as the world struggles to address entrenched deprivation, violent conflicts, and vulnerabilities to natural disasters, the pace of poverty reduction is beginning to slow down.
- The rate of extreme poverty in rural areas is three times higher than that in metropolitan areas.
- The year 2018 was the fourth hottest on record. In 2018, the concentration of CO₂ remained elevated.
- The state of the natural environment is rapidly declining.
- The sea level is increasing.
- The acidity of the ocean is increasing. The ocean's acidity has increased by 26% from pre-industrial times.
- One million species of plants and animals are in danger of being extinct.
- Unchecked land degradation persists.

Defining indicator: There aren't many indicators available in India to gauge the results of sustainable development. For instance, 86% of Indians, according to certain official statistics, have access to clean drinking water. However, the number of patients with illnesses that are water-prone and the number of deaths brought on by diarrhea plainly show that this is untrue. It indicates that absolutely no safe drinking water was supplied.

Financing sustainable development goals: The union government of India has declared that there will probably be a sizable budget gap unless states allocate a sizeable percentage of their resources to the social sector. Redistribution and rapid growth are not adequate. Not with standing significant economic development in 2010, one-third of the world's extremely poor reside in India alone, according to the United Nations MDG 2014 report. This suggests that, in addition to domestic resources, private finance may be a vital source of funding for the Sustainable Development Goals.

Ownership and monitoring: Keeping ownership in check is one of the biggest challenges to sustainability. According to current sources, NITI AAYOG is important for monitoring advancement. According to current sources, NITI AAYOG is important for monitoring advancement.

The AAYOG members, however, voiced doubts about their ability to handle this. Furthermore, it will need ownership at both the federal and state levels if states are expected to take the lead. and municipal level.

Lastly, but just as importantly, **tracking accomplishment progress** is a major obstacle to sustainable development in India. Measurement of sustainable development is nearly hard due to poor administrative data coverage, periodicity problems, and government choices that are sometimes made without enough data.

The Sustainable Development Goals for India had to combine targets for the environment and development into one set. However, the worldwide conferences are to blame for this, as there is an imbalance between development and environmental goals. Negative externalities are a necessary part of development without fruit sustainability.

Over 90% of agricultural biodiversity has been lost in many regions; half of the available water bodies are polluted and unusable for agricultural purposes; two thirds of the lands are degraded to various levels of sub-optimal productivity; air pollution is a dangerous factor in several Indian cities; and natural resources are found to be in decline and under stress in many countries. In India, air pollution poses a serious threat due to the overabundance of modern trash produced, including chemical and electrical waste. The most depressing news is that India's resources have already been utilized to double their biological capacity, and it is also discovered that its bio-capacity has been rapidly dropping for a few decades.

Since its national development goals are centered around sustainable development goals, India has been actively involved in implementing these goals. The catchphrase for India's national development agenda is widely regarded as "SABKA SAATH SABKA VIKASH," or "COLLECTIVE EFFORT, INCLUSIVE GROWTH," which was introduced by Prime Minister Narendra Modi. Incorporating social inclusion and poor people's empowerment, the objectives such as infrastructure development, economic growth, the fight against poverty and industrialization have fundamentally similar goals.

CURRENT INDIAN ECONOMY POSITION FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

- ❑ India has emerged as the fastest-growing major economy globally, surpassing the UK to claim the fifth position after a robust recovery from the shockwaves of the COVID-19 pandemic.
- ❑ The intricacies of this economic triumph are woven into the fabric of strong growth, global resilience, and optimistic projections that propel India into a new era of economic prominence.
- ❑ The opening quarter of the financial year 2023 witnessed a staggering 7.8 per cent growth in India's real Gross Domestic Product (GDP), reaching an estimated Rs 40.37 trillion (USD 484.94 billion).
- ❑ The resilience of the services sector is reflected in the impressive service exports, which stood at USD 164.89 billion for April- September 2023.
- ❑ In the first half of the current fiscal year, merchandise exports reached USD 211.40 billion, showcasing India's adeptness in navigating the intricate dynamics of international trade.
- ❑ India's nominal Gross Domestic Product (GDP) at current prices is estimated to be a formidable Rs. 301.75 trillion (USD 3.62 trillion) for the fiscal year 2023-24.
- ❑ India's commitment to sustainable development is evident in its focus on renewable energy. The government aims to achieve 40per cent of its energy from non-fossil sources by 2030. Moreover, India aspires to attain Net Zero Emissions by 2070 through a five-pronged strategy named 'Panchamrit.'
- ❑ In recognition of these efforts, India secured the 3rd position in the Renewable Energy Country Attractiveness Index
- ❑ The McKinsey Global Institute emphasizes the imperative for India to boost its rate of employment growth, aiming to create 90 million non-farm jobs between 2023 and 2030.
- ❑ The net employment rate needs to grow by 1.5 per cent per annum during this period to achieve a GDP growth target of 8-8.5 per cent. These insights underscore the intricate linkages between employment generation, productivity, and sustained economic growth.

- To sustain the growth momentum, the Indian government is proactively investing in capital spending on infrastructure and asset-building projects. In September 2023, the gross Goods and Services Tax (GST) revenue collection stood at Rs.1,62,712 crore (USD 19.54 billion). Cumulative Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) equity inflows to India stood at USD 937.58 billion between April 2000-June 2023. In August 2023, the overall Index of Industrial Production (IIP) stood at 145.1.

CONCLUSION

The Indian government, led by Prime Minister Narendra Modi, is putting a lot of effort into creating propaganda that will last in the country. The adoption of the Sustainable Development Goals in 2015, with a commitment to achieving these objectives by 2030, was one of his major initiatives. Again, privatization is an additional effort. Absent

Government cannot close the revenue gap and achieve its goals without the assistance of private institutions and organizations.

Today's administration has also implemented a number of policies, including education and training initiatives, in an effort to raise public understanding of environmental issues and lower the percentage of literacy. The current Indian government has implemented several initiatives, such as Made in India, Digital India, Swachh Bharat Abhiyan, The Jan Dhan Yojana, the ban on tobacco and plastic, the program to reduce poverty, the advancement of gender equality, and the solution to climate change. The prime minister has always committed to offer the necessary leadership and cooperation for the NITI AAYOG. The administration is acting to increase corruption and black money essential actions from time to time. The term "inclusive growth" receives adequate attention in the eleventh five-year plan.

To achieve sound sustainability, inclusive growth aids in closing social, economic, and environmental gaps.

As a result, the UNDP, together with other UN agencies, is actively working to promote and assist nations that are implementing sustainable and inclusive growth policies. Developing components include the private sector and civil society. The atmosphere, rainforests, and oceans are examples of environmental commons that need to be protected because they are important sources of natural resources and ecosystem services. To preserve, replenish, and utilize natural resources in a sustainable manner, all parties involved must cooperate. The food chain needs to change. extensive alterations to the legislation, cultural and societal values, and infrastructure that perpetuate the unsustainable status quo that exists now. It will need a far more thorough, swifter, and ambitious reaction to unleash the social and economic transformation required to meet our 2030 targets. The only way to achieve a far more positive future is to fundamentally alter development policies, incentives, and practices.

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